

Functional Trade-offs Asymmetrically Promote Phenotypic Evolution

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Supplementary Materials

EXTENDED METHODS AND MATERIALS

Sampling and Measurements

We measured 358 individuals representing 130 species of Neotropical cichlid (Table S1). Species were chosen to reflect all major lineages (López-Fernández et al. 2010; McMahan et al. 2013) and reflect their ecological diversity (Winemiller et al. 1995; López-Fernández et al. 2012; Říčan et al. 2016). Specimens were either cleared and stained or radiographed, permitting direct measurement of jaw bones. To characterize the trade-off between velocity- and force-modified jaw systems, we measured the lever mechanism of the lower jaw and calculated mechanical advantage as the in-lever divided by the out-lever (Wainwright and Richards 1995). Mechanical advantage depicts the potential force transfer to the tip of the lower jaw as the adductor mandibulae muscle contracts and closes the jaws (Wainwright et al. 2004; Figure 1a). Mechanical advantage of the jaw closing and opening levers were highly correlated based on phylogenetic least squares regression ($r=0.225$; $t=2.779$; $p=0.006$); therefore, we simply used the closing mechanical advantage values to characterize the velocity-force trade-off for all subsequent phylogenetic comparative analyses.

To characterize the size, shape, and protrusible nature of the jaw system, we measured the length of the lower jaw (mandible), maxilla, dentigerous arm of the premaxilla, and ascending process of the premaxilla (Table S1). All measurements follow Burress et al. (2020). The lower jaw was measured as the linear distance between the articular-quadrato joint and the anterior tip of the lower jaw. The maxilla was

measured as the linear distance between the maxilla-nasal joint and the opposing furthestmost tip of the maxilla. The dentigerous arm of the premaxilla was measured as the linear distance from the anterior midline of the premaxilla to the posterior-lateral tip of the maxilla. The ascending process of the maxilla was measured as the linear distance from the base of the dentition at the anterior midline to the tip of the ascending process. These traits have well-established associations with feeding performance and/or feeding ecology. The ascending process of the premaxilla is correlated with jaw protrusion (Hulsey et al. 2010; Burress et al. 2020), which varies along a gradient among species that feed on evasive to non-evasive prey (Waltzek and Wainwright 2003; Bellwood et al. 2015). The lower jaw and dentigerous arm of the premaxilla characterize the size of the jaws and vary predictably in response to feeding ecology, with predators and grazers possessing relatively larger and smaller jaws, respectively (Winemiller et al. 1995). The maxilla is one of the mobile links of the four-bar linkage system that describes the motion of the oral jaws during feeding (Hulsey and De León 2005). These traits were ln-transformed and regressed against ln-transformed standard body length and phylogenetically size-corrected using the *phyl.resid* function implemented in PHYTOOLS (Revell 2012). Standard length was measured as the linear distance from the anterior tip of the premaxilla to the posterior edge of the hypural plate.

Owing to subjectivity in determining the point at which one function trades-off for another, we utilized a sliding window approach to classify species as engaging in a trade-off in terms of velocity- or force-modified jaws. We used five different intervals to classify species as velocity-modified, no trade-off, and force-modified based on the closing mechanical advantage of the lower jaw: the fifth and 95th percentiles, 10th and 90th percentiles, 15th and 85th percentiles, 20th and 80th percentiles, and 25th and 75th percentiles (Figure S1). These sliding windows reflect varied degrees of trade-off, from extreme to modest (on average), respectively.

Phylogenetic Comparative Methods

During phylogenetic comparative analyses, we used the phylogeny of Burress and Tan (2017), later updated by Burress et al. (2019) to reflect the shifting understanding of cichlid divergence times (*i.e.*, Matschiner et al. 2017). This phylogeny densely sampled species (902 species) and is consistent with recent phylogenomic hypotheses of the Cichlinae (Burress et al. 2018; Ilves et al. 2018). The phylogeny was pruned to include the species represented in the morphological dataset. There is a more recent phylogeny that broadly sampled cichlids (McGee et al. 2020); we briefly demonstrate that our results are consistent using this alternative phylogeny, but otherwise limit its use because of the inclusion of morphological characters to infer the phylogeny.

We then estimated rates of jaw diversification for each of these discrete states using a Bayesian, state-dependent, relaxed-clock model of multivariate Brownian motion (MuSSCRat; May and Moore 2020) implemented in RevBayes (Höhna et al. 2016). This model jointly estimates the history of a discrete character and set of continuous characters, permits rates to vary among branches and among continuous characters. This method also accounts for background rate heterogeneity, which prevents all rate heterogeneity from being attributed to the discrete character and reduces the risk of falsely attributing rate variation to the discrete character of interest. Many factors can moderate the rate of phenotypic evolution, including genetic (Schluter 1996) and ecological features (Simpson 1953; Hunter 1988; Mahler et al. 2010). By accounting for background rate variation and thereby reducing the risk of erroneously interpreting the signal of these alternative factors (May and Moore 2020; Burress and Muñoz 2021), we were able to hone in on rate variation attributable to the velocity-force trade-off. We scrutinized the robustness of the MuSSCRat model in several ways. First, we repeated each model using different priors on the number of rate shifts (*i.e.*, 20, 60, and 100 shifts) to assess its impact on the posterior estimates of key parameters, including the number of rate shifts, number of state changes, and evolutionary rates for each state of the discrete character. Secondly, we employed MuSSCRat using both a random local clock (RLC) as well as an uncorrelated lognormal (UCLN) model (May and Moore 2020). Both are derived from relaxed clocks. The RLC assumes there is background rate variation at the root of the tree and that

branches have some probability of a rate shift. If there is no rate shift, the rate is inherited from its ancestral branch. This creates some phylogenetic structure to rate variation. Alternatively, the UCLN model assumes each branch has its own background rate variation, meaning that the rates of ancestor-descendant branches are uncorrelated (*i.e.*, the rates lack phylogenetic structure). Third, we repeat analyses using an alternative phylogeny that was recently published (McGee et al. 2020). Lastly, we verified that our results were not artefacts of the sliding window procedure by repeating the analyses (1) with simulated characters to inform the trade-off (*i.e.*, in lieu of mechanical advantage) and delineate the discrete character states paired with the empirical continuous characters, (2) the empirical discrete character paired with simulated continuous characters, and (3) simulated discrete and continuous characters. These data were simulated under Brownian motion using the fastBM function implemented in PHYTOOLS (Revell 2012).

We were considerate of the possibility that the pipeline in which we generated our sliding windows could partition the most extreme values of the continuous characters into the “trade-off” character states and perhaps systematically bias the estimates of evolutionary rates at the extreme if mechanical advantage was correlated with the continuous characters. Therefore, we tested this evolutionary correlation by calculating phylogenetic contrasts for mechanical advantage and multivariate phylogenetic contrasts (McPeck et al. 2008) of the continuous characters that reflect the shape of the jaw system. Contrasts were calculated using the pic function implemented in APE (Paradis 2012). We assessed significance of the correlation using robust regression, as contrasts often produce outliers that may obscure overall patterns (Slater and Pennell 2013).

We estimated the degree of selection (α) towards velocity- and force-modified jaws using OUwie function employed in the OUwie R package (Beaulieu et al. 2012; Beaulieu and O’Meara 2015). We estimated the evolutionary histories of the discrete characters using stochastic character mapping (Huelsenbeck et al. 2003) with the make-simmap function implemented in the PHYTOOLS package (Revell 2012). During this procedure, we allowed all transitions to have different rates (*i.e.*, the all-rates-

different model transition model; ARD) and we fit a multi-peak Ornstein-Uhlenbeck evolutionary model that permits different α for each state of the selective regime (*i.e.*, OUMA) with the regimes depicting velocity-modified jaws, jaws with no trade-off, and force-modified jaws. We estimated α across each of the aforementioned sliding windows and repeated these estimates across 100 trees randomly sampled from the posterior distribution to account for uncertainty in phylogenetic relationships and divergence times.

We were interested the degree of ecological lability along the velocity-force trade-off. We classified three guilds associated with velocity-modified jaws: piscivory, substrate sifting, and zooplanktivory (Hulsey and García de León 2005; Martinez et al. 2018; Burress et al. 2020). We also classified three guilds associated with force-modified jaws: algivory, detritivory, and herbivory (Říčan et al. 2016; Burress et al. 2020). We chose these feeding guilds and assigned species based on a combination of primary dietary and feeding kinematic literature (Winemiller et al. 1995; Wainwright et al. 2001; Waltzek and Wainwright 2003; Hulsey et al. 2010; Burress 2016; Říčan et al. 2016) as well as cross-validation with our estimates of mechanical advantage. For this analysis, all other species were classified as not exhibiting trade-offs. We defined an equal number of guilds to prevent one side of the velocity-force trade-off from arbitrarily having more opportunities for transitions. Since molluscs are mostly secondary or tertiary prey items (Winemiller et al. 1995; Burress 2016 and references therein), all species that eat molluscs in our dataset were represented by one of the other force-modified guilds that better reflect their primary diets. We estimated transition rates using stochastic character mapping as described above (Huelsenbeck et al. 2003; Revell 2012). We summarized the rates of three types of transitions: (1) transitions into a trade-off (no trade-offs to velocity- or force-associated feeding ecology), (2) transitions from a trade-off (velocity- or force-associated feeding ecology to no trade-offs), and (3) transitions within a trade-off (among feeding ecologies associated with the same trade-off).

To assess if phenotypic disparity along the velocity-force trade-off, we calculated multivariate jaw shape disparity for each of the sliding windows (*i.e.*, 95%, 90%, etc.) using the disparity function

implemented with the GEIGER package (Harmon et al. 2008). Disparity was calculated using mean squared distance. Lastly, we estimated the adaptive landscape on either side of the velocity-force trade-off, specifically the distribution of adaptive peaks, using the I1ou package (Khabbazian et al. 2016). Using the *estimate_shift_configuration* function, we fit multi-peak OU models to our four continuous characters that characterize the shape and size of the oral jaws. We then summarized the proportion of optima represented within each sliding window (*i.e.*, 95%, 90%, etc.). Our intent in doing so was to quantify the implications of the velocity-force trade-off in terms of viable evolutionary optima, specifically a loss of viable optima towards the extremes of the trade-off and potential asymmetries in this loss in each direction. We repeated this exercise across 100 trees randomly sampled from the posterior distribution to account for phylogenetic uncertainty.

Table S1. The data is archived on dryad.

Table S2. Summary of the posterior probabilities that the rates of jaw evolution are state-dependent from MuSSCRat models using empirical and simulated data across different degrees of trade-off.

Model	Percentiles				
	05/95	10/90	15/85	20/80	25/75
LRC ₂₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
LRC ₆₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
LRC ₁₀₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
UCLN	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.982	0.279
McGee ₂₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
McGee ₆₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
McGee ₁₀₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Simulated _{discrete}	0.549	0.258	0.578	0.512	0.448
Simulated _{continuous}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Simulated _{discrete+continuous}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Footnote: Local random clock (LRC) model with different priors on the number of rate shifts (20, 60, and 100) (depicted in the main text), uncorrelated log-normal (UCLN) model, LRC model using an alternative phylogeny from McGee et al. (2020) (McGee) with different priors on the number of rate shifts (20, 60, and 100), and LRC model using a simulated discrete trait (disc), simulated continuous traits (cont), or both.

Figure S1. Hypothetical relationships between the velocity-force trade-off and diversification of the jaw system. Lines depict alternative relationships within each general type. Solid/dashed and black/gray scale used only to accentuate the different lines and have no inherent meaning.

Figure S2. Sliding windows used for delineating the thresholds for trading-off along values of mechanical advantage: the top and bottom 5th, 10th, 15th, 20th, and 25th percentiles. These sliding windows depict more to less of a trade-off, on average, respectively.

Figure S3. Estimates of selection (α) towards trading-off in terms of velocity and force (a). Estimates of selection along sliding windows depict the extent of trading off for velocity (b) or force (c). More restrictive percentiles (*i.e.*, darker colors) depict a harsher trade-off, on average. Distributions reflect estimates of alpha across 100 phylogenetic trees randomly sampled from the posterior distribution.

Figure S4. Assessment of robustness of the MuSSCRat analyses and the estimates of key parameters: the number of rate shifts (a), number of state changes (b), velocity state rates (c), no trade-off state rate (d), and force state rate (e). These results correspond to the models shown in the main text of the paper, in which MuSSCRat was run using a random local clock. For results with an alternative model, see Figures S5 and S6.

Figure S5. Estimates of state-dependent rates of jaw evolution using an uncorrelated lognormal (UCLN) model during the implementation of MuSSCRat. Posterior probability (PP) that the rates are state-dependent. Note that the results shown in the main text uses a random local clock (RLC) model, with the same results, except for the most inclusive sliding window (*i.e.*, the 25th and 75th percentiles) in which the rates were not state-dependent using the UCLN model. The magnitude of the state-dependence (*i.e.*, rate ratios) declined across the sliding windows (*i.e.*, moving from more restrictive to more inclusive) in the LRC model, but the rates were state-dependent in all runs across all sliding windows (see Figure 4 in the main text).

Figure S6. Rate ratios of velocity and force-modified jaws relative to those with no trade-off, estimated with an uncorrelated lognormal (UCLN) model. Note that the 25th and 75th percentiles are not shown because the rates were not state-dependent (see Figure S4). Compare with Figure 4 in the main text using a random local clock (RLC) model.

Figure S7. Evolutionary optima across the Neotropical cichlid phylogeny estimated with a multipeak OU model. Asterisks denote shifts to new optima. Bar plots depict the relative values of traits: premaxilla (PM), maxilla (M), ascending process (AP), and mandible (OL).

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